

ANTIBIOTIC DISPENSING AND AMR AWARENESS AMONG COMMUNITY PHARMACISTS: INSIGHTS FROM A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Objectives: Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is an escalating global issue, and understanding its drivers in community pharmacy settings is essential for developing contextual interventions. This study aimed to explore antibiotic dispensing practices, AMR awareness, patient interactions, and training needs of community pharmacists.

Methods: A qualitative study was carried out in Mysuru City, Karnataka, India, involving in-depth, semi-structured interviews with community pharmacists. Participants were selected using a convenience sampling method. The interview guide underwent pilot testing, and the final sample size was determined based on data saturation. All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed word to word. Data were analysed using a thematic analysis approach, aligning with the study's objectives.

Result: Four major themes were identified: (1) Knowledge and awareness of AMR; (2) Antibiotic dispensing practices; (3) Patient-pharmacist interactions; and (4) Training needs and capacity building. While pharmacists demonstrated a basic understanding of AMR, non-prescription dispensing of antibiotics such as amoxicillin, azithromycin, and ciprofloxacin was common, often driven by customer demand. Many pharmacists agreed that they do partial course dispensing and have a lack of follow-up with patients. Awareness of regulatory protocols like Schedule H/H1 existed, but adherence was inconsistent. Participants expressed strong interest in AMR-related training, favouring flexible formats such as evening workshops or online sessions in local languages.

Conclusion: Community pharmacists in Mysuru demonstrated limited adherence to prescription regulations despite basic AMR awareness. Strengthening pharmacist training and enforcing stewardship policies are essential to curb inappropriate antibiotic dispensing.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance, community pharmacists, antibiotics, qualitative study, antimicrobial stewardship, dispensing practices

Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is considered a major global health challenge of the 21st century, with estimates suggesting it could result in 10 million deaths each year by 2050 if not effectively tackled [1]. The COVID-19 pandemic has intensified the silent pandemic of antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Many complex interconnected factors accelerate AMR, with the evaluation of the contextual drivers essential for designing effective interventions [2].

Dispensing Antibiotics without Medical Prescription is a key cause of AMR in Low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), like India. While community pharmacists are generally aware of AMR, studies have shown that inappropriate dispensing continues to be widespread. In India, where access to public healthcare can be limited or inconsistent, patients often turn to community pharmacies for self-medication. This widespread reliance on pharmacies increases the risk of irrational antibiotic use [3].

A study across 28 LMICs identified poor regulation, lack of qualified pharmacists, commercial pressures, consumer demand, and limited AMR awareness as key factors driving non-prescription antibiotic sales. In contrast, pharmacists in high-income countries (HICs) often serve as gatekeepers, guided by structured Antimicrobial Stewardship (AMS) frameworks and supported by continuing professional development (CPD) and regulation. Multifaceted AMS training in HICs has been shown to improve patient communication, adherence promotion, and rational use of antibiotics [4,5].

India's National Action Plan (NAP) on AMR, aligned with the WHO Global Action Plan, provides a strategic roadmap for AMS. However, implementation has been hampered by decentralisation, limited funding, and fragmented stakeholder engagement [6]. Initiatives like the ICMR's Standard Treatment Guidelines and the Red Line campaign were introduced to discourage non-prescription sales, but studies show that their impact has been limited due to poor enforcement and awareness [7,8].

Understanding the perspectives and daily practices of community pharmacists is crucial to advancing AMS efforts in the Indian context. While quantitative surveys provide prevalence estimates, qualitative research is necessary to uncover the behavioural, systemic, and contextual factors that influence antibiotic dispensing. There remains a gap in such research, particularly in urban and semi-urban Indian settings like Mysuru, where community pharmacists serve a diverse patient population with varying levels of healthcare access.

Materials and Methods

Study design and setting:

This qualitative study involved semi-structured interviews with community pharmacists practising in Mysuru City, Karnataka, India. Participants were licensed pharmacists working in community pharmacy with at least one year of experience and expressed willingness to participate.

Study Instrument:

The interview guide used in the study was developed by the research team following an extensive review of relevant literature [9-11]. It was designed to address the identified research questions and existing knowledge gaps. The guide was initially piloted with three pharmacists to assess clarity, face validity, and consistency. These pilot interviews were excluded from the final analysis. Based on emerging insights during data collection, the interview guide was revised to better capture evolving themes in subsequent interviews.

Data Collection:

Participants were recruited through convenience sampling. Pharmacists were then approached based on their availability and willingness to take part. All interviews were conducted by RR at the respective pharmacies between January and March 2024. Prior to each interview, participants were briefed about the study's objectives and procedures, and written informed consent was obtained.

Demographic details were also collected and included details such as age, gender, educational qualification, and years of experience. Interviews were conducted in Kannada, the regional language, and were audio recorded. Observational notes were also taken during each session. The final sample size was determined by data saturation.

Data analysis:

All the recorded interviews were anonymised, transcribed, and translated into English, and the identity of the respondents was kept confidential to ensure complete privacy. Thematic analysis was used for generating initial codes, and the coded data were reviewed to develop themes. Codes and themes were continuously reviewed and revised through discussion among the core writing team of authors.

Ethical approval:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee, JSS Medical College, JSS Academy of Higher Education and Research, Mysore (No. JSSMC/IEC/11523/16/NCT/2023-24). Written consent was obtained from study participants.

Results

A detailed description of all the interviewees is presented in **Table 1**. A total of 12 interviews were conducted, with interview durations ranging from 19 to 47 minutes and a mean duration of 28 minutes (SD = 8.5 min). Among the participants, 8 (66.7%) were males and 4 (33.3%) were females. The mean age of the interviewed pharmacists was 31.75 ± 7.12 years. Regarding qualifications, the majority held a Diploma in Pharmacy (75%), while the remaining 25% had a Bachelor's degree in Pharmacy. Participants' work experience ranged from 1 to 16 years, with 25% having 11–15 years of experience, 25% having 6–10 years, and 50% having 1–5 years

Table 1: Demographics of the participants (N=12)

Respondent	Gender	Age (years)	Experience (years)	Educational qualification	Interview duration (minutes)
Pharmacist 1	Female	29	6	D. Pharm	37
Pharmacist 2	Male	45	13	D. Pharm	28
Pharmacist 3	Female	25	2	B. Pharm	25
Pharmacist 4	Male	26	3	B. Pharm	22
Pharmacist 5	Male	37	8	D. Pharm	47
Pharmacist 6	Male	24	2	B. Pharm	29
Pharmacist 7	Female	44	16	D. Pharm	24
Pharmacist 8	Male	36	11	D. Pharm	26
Pharmacist 9	Female	23	1	D. Pharm	29
Pharmacist 10	Male	28	4	D. Pharm	32
Pharmacist 11	Male	33	7	D. Pharm	19
Pharmacist 12	Male	31	5	D. Pharm	26

Using reflexive thematic analysis as proposed by Braun and Clarke [12], four themes with corresponding sub-themes were identified and mentioned in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Themes and sub-themes from transcribed SSIs

Themes	Subthemes
Knowledge & awareness of AMR	1.1 Understanding of AMR
	1.3 Necessity to prevent AMR

Antibiotic dispensing practices	2.1 Common infections for which antibiotics are dispensed
	2.2 Dispensing antibiotics without a prescription
	2.3 Adherence to regulatory protocols (E.g. Schedule H)
	2.4 Influence of customer demand
Patient-Pharmacist interactions	3.1 Completion of antibiotic course by patients
	3.2 Observations on patient behaviour
	3.3 Nature of queries from patients regarding antibiotics
	3.4 Counselling provided on antibiotic usage and completion of course
Training Needs and Capacity Building	4.1 Interest in AMR-related training
	4.2 Preferred training formats

Theme I: Knowledge of AMR

Interviews with community pharmacists from Mysuru revealed varying levels of understanding and awareness of AMR. While some participants demonstrated a basic conceptual grasp, others acknowledged the growing importance of AMR prevention in public health.

1.1. Understanding of AMR

Most pharmacists described AMR as a situation where antibiotics become ineffective over time due to inappropriate use. Their explanations, although not technical, showed an awareness of the problem at a functional level.

"Microorganisms causing the infection develop resistance and the antibiotic will not be effective..."(P3)

"It means antibiotics won't work for that. We call it as antibiotic resistance." (P10)

Subtheme 1.2: Necessity to Prevent AMR

Pharmacists acknowledged the importance of addressing antibiotic resistance, often linking it to patient behaviour and the need for education.

"Yes, we need to prevent antibiotic resistance, first we need to educate the patients" (P8)

Theme II: Antibiotic Dispensing Practices

All twelve participants acknowledged that antibiotics were frequently dispensed for common infections, and many admitted that these were often sold without a prescription. While some were initially hesitant to admit this practice, further probing revealed that dispensing without prescriptions was widespread in the community pharmacy setting.

Subtheme 2.1: Common infections for which antibiotics are dispensed

Pharmacists reported that most customers approached them for treatment of minor ailments such as cough, fever, diarrhoea, or skin infections. In such cases, antibiotics like azithromycin, amoxicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanate, ciprofloxacin, cefixime, cefpodoxime, and various combinations were dispensed routinely.

"People come with cough and fever and ask directly for azithromycin or amoxicillin—they don't want to go to the doctor every time." (P7)

"Amoxicillin potassium clavulanate, cefpodoxime, cefixime, ciprofloxacin, ciprofloxacin + tinidazole, norfloxacin + tinidazole are most commonly dispensed antibiotics." (P5)

Subtheme 2.2: Dispensing antibiotics without a prescription

Even though these are classified as Schedule H drugs requiring prescriptions, the dispensing was often done based on prior patient experience or symptom description alone.

Although some pharmacists initially hesitated to admit non-prescription antibiotic sales, further probing revealed that drugs such as amoxicillin-clavulanate, cefpodoxime, ciprofloxacin, and combinations like ciprofloxacin + tinidazole were frequently dispensed without prescriptions.

"Amoxicillin potassium clavulanate, cefpodoxime, cefixime, ciprofloxacin, ciprofloxacin + tinidazole, norfloxacin + tinidazole are most commonly dispensed antibiotics." (P3)

"If prescription is written within 15 days we will dispense, if it's older than 15 days we ask them to consult the doctor and to bring the prescription." (P1)

This practice was often driven by customer expectations of quick relief, and in many instances, only 2–4 tablets were given, especially when patients reported previous use or showed strips of earlier prescriptions.

Subtheme 2.3: Adherence to Regulatory Protocols (e.g., Schedule H)

While participants were aware of the regulations surrounding Schedule H drugs, many openly admitted that compliance was low. They pointed out that although prescription maintenance was practiced for certain medicines, antibiotics were an exception.

"We are supposed to take prescriptions for Schedule H drugs, but in practice, most pharmacies don't follow it strictly." (P4)

"Yes, it is maintained, but we are specifically not maintaining for antibiotics." (P1)

Pharmacists highlighted that one of the major reasons for non-prescription sales was the persistent demand from customers. They explained that refusal to dispense would often result in losing regular customers to competitors.

"They expect immediate relief. If we refuse to give the medicine, they say they'll just get it from the next shop." (P9)

"Even if we try to explain that antibiotics are not needed, they insist, saying 'This always works for me—just give it.'" (P11)

Subtheme 2.3: Influence of Customer Demand on Dispensing Practices

Customer expectations played a major role in the pharmacists' decision to dispense antibiotics. Several participants admitted that pressure from customers often led them to provide antibiotics without prescriptions to avoid losing business.

"They expect immediate relief. If we refuse to give the medicine, they say they'll just get it from the next shop." (P12)

"Even if we try to explain that antibiotics are not needed, they insist, saying 'This always works for me—just give it.'" (P7)

Theme 3: Patient–Pharmacist Interactions on Antibiotic Use

Interviews with community pharmacists in Mysuru revealed critical insights into how patients engage with pharmacy staff regarding antibiotics. The findings highlighted poor adherence to treatment, limited patient knowledge, and the often-reactive nature of counselling in the community pharmacy setting.

Subtheme 3.1. Completion of Antibiotic Course by Patients

Pharmacists unanimously reported that most patients do not complete the full course of antibiotics. Many patients stop taking medicines once symptoms subside, often within two or three days, even if they had purchased more tablets.

"Nobody consumes the full course of antibiotics; they say that they will consume but many don't consume."(P2) (NP1)

"Patients buy only 3 to 4 tablets for 2 days because they have experienced that after consuming one or two tablets their symptoms will be reduced."(P6)

3.2. Observations on Patient Behaviour

Pharmacists frequently observed self-diagnosis among patients. Many approached the pharmacy demanding specific antibiotics that had worked for them or someone they knew in the past. Several pharmacists also noted a pattern of patients consulting multiple sources including doctors, friends, and online information before coming to the pharmacy.

"Many patients self-diagnose and come asking for antibiotics they've used before, without even telling symptoms." (P8)

"People here often mix multiple doctor opinions and buy medicines based on what they hear from friends or relatives." (P9)

3.3. Nature of Queries from Patients Regarding Antibiotics

When asked about patient queries, pharmacists noted that the majority of customers do not seek detailed information. Only a few, often more educated or health-conscious, inquired about side effects, dosage, or medicine interactions.

"Only a few educated customers ask if the medicine has side effects or whether it's safe to take with other tablets."(P7)

3.4. Counselling Provided on Antibiotic Use and Course Completion

Counselling practices varied among pharmacists. While most admitted to providing only minimal advice due to time constraints or workload, a few made efforts to counsel when patients asked specific questions. Advice on completing the full course was commonly given, but adherence was not tracked.

"Usually, we don't counsel the patient as we don't get enough time, but if the patient asks what this antibiotic or medicine is for, we'll give advice and ask them to complete the course." (P4)

"We advise them to complete the full course of antibiotics, that's all. If they say we don't want this much, only that amount we dispense. Few people say that they'll buy it later." (P2)

Theme 4: Training Needs and Capacity Building of Pharmacists

The study also explored pharmacists' perspectives on professional development and their interest in strengthening antibiotic stewardship practices through training.

4.1. Interest in AMR-Related Training

Many participants expressed interest in structured training programmes focused on rational antibiotic use and antimicrobial resistance. They acknowledged a lack of formal training post-graduation and showed a willingness to learn more to serve patients better.

"We need training on when to give antibiotics and when not to." (P1)

"I'm interested in learning more about AMR because customers ask many questions now, and we need to answer confidently." (P6)

This finding supports the need for continuous professional development (CPD) modules for pharmacists in primary healthcare systems.

4.2. Preferred Training Formats

When asked about preferred formats, pharmacists favoured flexible options such as evening workshops or online sessions in local languages. Business hours and daily responsibilities made it difficult for them to attend lengthy or off-site sessions.

"Short workshops in the evenings or online sessions in the local language would be useful—we can't leave the shop for long." (P5)

"In-person training is good, but we cannot come to a place where you conduct it as it affects our business." (P2)

Discussion

This study used exploratory qualitative methods to identify factors contributing to AMR across urban and rural community pharmacy settings in Karnataka, India. In studies conducted in India, many pharmacists admit to selling antibiotics without valid prescriptions. Additionally, partial antibiotic dosages are routinely dispensed illegally [13]. The interviewed pharmacists were aware of antibiotic resistance, but not its drivers. India implemented Schedule H1 in 2014 to restrict pharmaceutical dispensing, requiring a pharmacy to maintain a separate Register to record Schedule H1 medicines dispensed. The Drugs and Cosmetics Rules in India shifted 46 drugs from Schedule H to Schedule H1, 34 of which were antimicrobials. Schedule H and H1 antibiotics cannot be dispensed without a prescription, including expired ones [14,15]. However, in this study, despite knowing that Schedule H drugs require prescriptions, pharmacists admitted that enforcement of these rules is weak. Similar findings were observed in studies conducted in other places in India. In general, the situation in India indicates a widespread disregard for the norms that control the sale of antibiotics with a prescription. [16-18]

Dispensing antibiotics without a prescription has been a common practice among pharmacists and non-pharmacists across many states of India. In our study also, participants commonly reported dispensing antibiotics like amoxicillin, amoxicillin + -clavulanic acid, azithromycin, cefixime, cefpodoxime, ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin, norfloxacin + tinidazole, ciprofloxacin + tinidazole for self-limiting conditions such as cold, cough, fever, and diarrhoea without a prescription. Similarly, in-depth interviews conducted in other states such as Andhra Pradesh and Haryana, point out a high percentage of dispensing being practiced by informal practitioners. [19-21] In a systematic review consisting of 84 studies, it was observed that 60% of the antibiotics were dispensed without a prescription [14].

In our study, many participants did not follow-up with patients after dispensing antibiotics, because of a reported lack of time. On the contrary, in a study conducted in Nepal, 65% of community pharmacists reported that they followed-up on patients who were dispensed antibiotics [22]. The Follow-up with patients after dispensing medicines is an important task for community pharmacy staff. As a part of proper dispensing practice, follow-up improves patients' understanding of medication adherence, reduces AMR, and protects patients' safety resulting in better patient outcomes [23].

Participants in our study reported that patients self-medicate and also use old/ expired prescriptions. Similar findings have also been reported in the literature [9,24] where more than 70% of participants interviewed stated that patients often purchased antibiotics for a short duration, based on their perception that their symptoms will soon improve. Thus, this practice of consumers, as well as of pharmacists, leads to the irrational consumption of antibiotics in the community.

One of the participants reported that individuals who seek medical assistance may consult multiple doctors after just beginning treatment with an antimicrobial, even after just one or two pills, if they do not experience immediate relief. This behavior is influenced by factors such as doctor-patient interactions, including dissatisfaction with the initial consultation and dissatisfied patients not finding a "magic" remedy [25]. This type of irresponsible use of antibiotics, both prescribed and not prescribed, can lead to an increase in AMR.

Maintaining knowledge of rational dispensing practices by requiring pharmacists to complete CPD to keep their licenses is a strategy for rational antibiotic use. Pharmacy legislation in LMICs should require inventory control and mandatory dispensing reports for inspection and cross-verification of valid prescriptions for antimicrobials to be maintained in pharmacies. These measures could significantly reduce AMR and antibiotic abuse by improving accountability of rational dispensing practices particularly as retail pharmacies are profit-driven and antibiotic demand has shifted to these less controlled environments, leading to inappropriate antibiotic sales.

This study has several limitations that should be considered while interpreting the findings. The data were self-reported during interviews and may be influenced by social desirability bias, with participants potentially underreporting inappropriate dispensing practices or overstating their awareness of AMR. The study did not include direct observation of dispensing practices, which could have provided additional validation or contrast to the interview findings. Additionally, informal or unlicensed pharmacy staff, who often play a significant role in antibiotic dispensing in India, were not included in the study.

Conclusion

This study highlights key behavioural, systemic, and knowledge-related drivers of irrational antibiotic dispensing among community pharmacists in Mysuru. Despite having basic knowledge of AMR, pharmacists continue to dispense antibiotics without prescriptions, driven by customer demand and weak enforcement of regulatory protocols. Patients' self-medication practices, partial course consumption, and minimal counselling further exacerbate the issue. Capacity-building efforts, such as AMR-focused training and CPD programmes tailored to pharmacists' work realities, are essential. Regulatory reinforcement and patient education campaigns must go hand-in-hand with pharmacist training to ensure sustainable antimicrobial stewardship in community settings.

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